

ESSENTIAL AND PRODUCTIVE WAY FOR DEVELOPING READING SKILLS

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Abstract. *This article is about essential and productive ways of developing reading skills. The main idea of this article is the importance of reading in human beings life and why we need it or in which situation we rely on reading skills and in what way we can improve our reading ability. Children can easily improve their reading skills with the help of this article which describes the most crucial and useful method of reading skills.*

Key words: *Reading, comprehension, skimming, scanning, vocabulary, retention, decoding, fluency and inference.*

Аннотация. *Эта статья о необходимом и продуктивном способе развития навыков чтения. Основная идея этой статьи - важность чтения в жизни человека и почему оно нам нужно или в какой ситуации мы полагаемся на навыки чтения и каким образом мы можем улучшить свои способности к чтению. С помощью этой статьи дети могут легко улучшить свои навыки чтения, потому что в этой статье описывается наиболее важный и полезный метод развития навыков чтения.*

Ключевые слова: *Чтение, понимание, беглый просмотр, сканирование, словарный запас, удержание, декодирование, беглость и умозаключение.*

Annotasiya. *Ushbu maqola o'qish qobiliyatini rivojlantirishning muhim va samarali usuliga bag'ishlanadi. Ushbu maqolaning asosiy g'oyasi - o'qishning inson hayotidagi ahamiyati, qanday vaziyatlarda o'qish qobiliyatiga tayanish va qanday yaxshilash haqida. Bolalar ushbu maqola yordamida o'qish qobiliyatlarini osongina yaxshilashlari mumkin, chunki ushbu maqolada o'qish qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishning eng muhim va foydali usuli tasvirlangan.*

Kalitso'zlar: *O'qish, tushunish, ravonlik, skanerlash, lug'at, saqlash, dekodlash, ravonlik va xulosa chiqarish.*

What is reading itself and why do we need reading skills?

1. Definition of Reading

Reading is a part of language skills that is important to learn for students because reading can help them to get a lot of information. According to Hill (2000:65) reading is a process by which a student obtains the information he or she needs from the study material and it requires the evaluation and analysis the idea expressed by the author. Another expert described the reading skill like this: "As an enjoyable, intensive, private activity from which much pleasure can be derived, and in which one can become totally absorbed." (Alderson, 2000:13)

Reading is the process of looking at a series of written symbols and getting meaning from them. When we read, we use our eyes to receive written symbols (letters, punctuation marks and spaces) and use our brain to convert them into words, sentences and paragraphs that notify something to us. Reading can be done in a silent way or aloud. Reading is a receptive skill through it we receive information. But the complex process of reading also requires the skill of speaking, so that we can pronounce the words that we read. In this sense, reading is also a productive skill from which we receive information and transmit it and how much information you get from reading depends on each person. According to Patel and Jain (2008:113-114), reading is an important activity in life which one can update knowledge or it is not only a database of information and interesting lessons, but also expands and strengthens someone's knowledge within a language. The skill of reading is developed in societies with literary taste, as it can lead to develop comprehension and enrich vocabulary. The problem in the reading skill is comprehension. It is challenging for students to understand the meaning of the text and they cannot focus on what they read during the reading activity and still have difficulty to get the plot of the text. The another problem is that not every detail of information in the passage is needed to answer the reading questions but students usually read the reading passage word by word. It is also important for students to study the text in class in order to find out the way of using the language, the number of paragraphs namely the content and the usage of relative clauses. We must give the students a chance to respond to that message in some way, especially they should be allowed to show their feelings about the topic and to provoke personal engagement in the language. How well the students are able to deal with the reading material will depend on whether the text is designed for intensive or extensive reading. We are aware of that the term intensive reading refers to reading skill.

Reading skills are abilities that pertain to a person's capacity to read, comprehend, interpret and decode written language and texts. Exceptional reading skills can be highly beneficial for assimilating and responding to written

communications like emails, messages, letters and other written messages. Using reading skills in the workplace can also be important for ensuring effective written communication, which can result in less miscommunication or misunderstanding of expectations.

What is reading comprehension?

Definition of Reading Comprehension. Reading comprehension is how to get information in reading students understanding or comprehend the content of the subject that they read. According to Indrayani hasstated that reading comprehension as the process to get precise understanding of the writer's message trough simultaneously extracting and constructing meaning by collaborating reader's background knowledge and interaction and involvement. Reading comprehension is not just a receptive process, it implies a complex process in which the reader identify basic information and are able to predict, to infer, to argue, and to recognize writers' points of view. According to Partnership (2005) cited in Diaz, S&Laguado, J (2013:137), reading comprehension is about understanding a text which is read through the process of constructing meaning from a text. Lems (2010:170) also stated that reading comprehension is not a static competency. And Ahuja (2001 in Mohammad, 1999:27) mentioned that there are three levels of comprehension. The first level is literal comprehension. Comprehension of this level involves surface meaning. At this level, the students can be asked to find information and ideas that are explicitly stated in the text. The second level is interpretive or referential comprehension, at this level students go beyond what is said and read for deeper meanings. They must be able to read critically and analyze carefully what they have read. This level includes thinking process such as drawing conclusions, making generalizations and predicting outcomes. Finally, the third level of comprehension is critical reading where ideas and information are evaluated. At this level, the teacher can test student's ability to differentiate fact and opinion, the ability to recognize persuasive statements, and the ability to judge the accuracy of the information given in the text.

Reading comprehension is simply the ability to understand what you read. Strong reading comprehension typically encompasses a variety of literacy skills needed to interpret and identify meanings within a text. Several elements like fluency, the ability to decode unfamiliar vocabulary and using context clues from the reading to identify key features of a text can all be components of effective reading comprehension. The essential skills needed for reading comprehension include: Decoding, fluency, vocabulary, inference, retention.

How to improve reading skills?

There are a variety of ways you might improve your reading skills. You might practice speed reading to improve your fluency or make notes each time you encounter unfamiliar vocabulary. The following steps also help outline what you might do to improve and further develop your reading skills.

a) Set aside time to read each day b) Set reading goals c) Preview the texts you read d) Determine the purpose e) Apply key reading strategies f) Take notes while reading.

Apply what you read by summarizing.

Some people think of the act of reading as a straightforward task that's easy to master. In reality, reading is a complex process that draws on many different skills. Together, these skills lead to the ultimate goal of reading: reading comprehension or understanding what's been read.

Reading comprehension can be challenging for lots of reasons. Whatever the reason is knowing which skill your child is struggling with will support him and show him the right way.

It is justified that reading is considered as the ultimate skill to be used for collaboration at school and throughout life. It is crucial to look for information in order to read books. English is mandatory and often used as the medium of instruction in higher education. Reading (Anderson, Hiebert, Scott, & Wilkinson 1985) is a vital life skill, which ensures a child's success in school and even throughout his life. Children need to learn different reading strategies in primary sections (Sultana & Ahsan, 2013). If a child is not habituated and acquires the reading skill his personal achievement and job success certainly will be lost (1985). Thus, reading is being given importance in the realm of education sector. It is also considered as one of the most challenging areas, which requires more attention in any education institution. Analytical and critical reading is imperative if they want the possible outcome from the materials they are assigned for. The basic idea of this is to understand the purpose and the author's intention, when reading something. In fact, reading consists of two layers of reality: one that we can see and one that we cannot see. Thus, the goal of reading is to make the invisible layer and the underlying meaning visible and clear (Kose, 2006). Teele states that the objective of all readers should be to comprehend what they read (2004, p. 92). In this study it shows that among readers those who are good at reading are actively involved in reading. They are involved with the text and conscious of the procedures that they practice to understand what they read. Teachers can assist their students in improving their reading comprehension by giving instruction of reading strategies like predicting, making affiliation,

envisaging, inferring, questioning, summarizing, and so on (Block & Israel, 2005). It is also important for the teachers to teach the strategies by naming the strategy, to clarify the implemented strategy in the process of shaping through our minds out aloud group practice, partner practice, and autonomous use of the strategy (Duke & Pearson, 2005). According to Amin, R (2018) and using multimedia projector as visuals draw more attention among the students in reading. Various visual aids like images and videos help the students to understand the conceptual prospect of the text. Moreover, visual aids create a real relation between the readers and the text. It makes the reading process quicker and lively as cited (Yunus, Salehi & John (2013).

It is not an easy task to become a good reader. For this, first of all, learners need to set a goal for their reading. Good readers always have a purpose for reading. One of the basic approaches for developing comprehension skill is predicting which assists the readers set a purpose for their reading. It is evident that good readers utilize their experiences and knowledge to make predictions and formulate ideas as they read (Block & Israel, 2005). This approach also includes the student interaction that creates a sense of interest among others and improves their understanding of the text. A comparison between the outcome of the actual text and the prediction process will guide the learner to develop his understanding of the text. Some of the approaches for teaching prediction are modeling, predicting throughout the text with associates with a graphic planner or using post-it notes all through the content. Moreover, using title, table of contents, pictures and key words are also the integral parts of the prediction approach. Another key prediction approach is to give the students task of predicting at specific points through the text, assess the prediction, and review predictions if necessary (Teele, 2004). By first skimming a text, you can get a sense of its overall logical progression. Skimming can also help you make decisions about where to place your greatest focus when you have limited time for your reading. Here is one technique for skimming a text. You may need to modify it to suit your own reading style. First, prior to skimming, use some of the previewing techniques.

Then, read carefully the introductory paragraph, or perhaps the first two paragraphs. Ask yourself what the focus of the text appears to be, and try to predict the direction of the coming explanations or arguments.

Read carefully the first one or two sentences of each paragraph, as well as the concluding sentence or sentences.

Between these opening and closing sentences, keep your eyes moving and try to avoid looking up unfamiliar words or terminology. Your goal is to pick up the larger concepts and something of the overall pattern and significance of the text.

Read the concluding paragraph or paragraphscarefully. What does the author's overall purpose seem to be? Remember that you may be mistaken, so be prepared to modify your answer.

Finally, return to the beginning and read through the text carefully, noting the complexities you missed in your skimming and filling in the gaps in your understanding. Think about your purpose in reading this text and what you need to retain from it, and adjust your focus accordingly. Look up the terms you need to know, or unfamiliar words that appear several times.

Scanning is basically skimming with a more tightly focused purpose: but as for skimming is used to locate a particular fact or figure, or to see whether this text mentions a subject you're researching. Scanning is essential in the writing of research papers, when you may need to look through many articles and books in order to find the material you need. Keep a specific set of goals in mind as you scan the text, and avoid becoming distracted by other material. You can note what you'd like to return to later when you do have time to read further, and use scanning to move ahead in your research project".

Definition of Scanning and Skimming

a. Scanning

Scanning is another useful tool for speeding up your reading. Unlike skimming, when scanning you look only for a specific fact or piece of information without reading everything. You scan when you look for your favorite show listed in the cable guide, for your friend's phone number in a telephone book, and for the sports scores in the newspaper. For scanning to be successful, you need to understand the structure of the material and you should comprehend what you read in order to find out lo the specific information you need. It is also available to get details thoroughly and in no time.

How do we make use of scanning?

As we scan a lot of different types of materials in a daily life, the details about scanning will be learnt easily. It is also essential for a reader to establish his purpose, to locate the appropriate material and to know how the information is structured .

The material you scan is typically arranged in the following ways: alphabetically, chronologically, non-alphabetically, by category, or textually.

Alphabetical information is arranged in order from A to Z, while chronological information is arranged in time or in numerical order.

Information can also be arranged in non- alphabetical order, such as a television listing, or by category, listings of like items such as an auto parts catalog. Sometimes information is located within the written paragraphs of the text known as a textual sense as in an encyclopedia entry.

Learning to use your hands while scanning is very helpful in locating specific information. Do you do anything with your hands to locate a word in a dictionary? Do you find a meeting time on your calendar? Do you read a train or bus schedule? Using your hand or finger is extremely helpful in focusing your attention and keeping your place while scanning a column of material. Your peripheral vision can also assist you to scan effectively. When your hand moves down a list of names, you see not only the name your finger is pointing to, but also the names which are above and below. Let your eyes work for you when searching for information.

b. Skimming

Skimming is one of the tools you can use to read more in less time. It refers to looking only for the general or main ideas, and works best with non-fiction (or factual) material. With skimming, your overall understanding is reduced because you don't read everything thoroughly. You read only what is important to your purpose. Skimming is only used to get the main idea. How do we make use of skimming?

A lot of people think that skimming is a haphazard process placing the eyes wherever glance is cast. However, for skimming effectively there has to be a structure but everything is read. What you read is more important than what you leave out. So what material is read and what material is left out?

For instance, you are doing research on a long chapter or a web site, by reading the first few paragraphs in detail, you will get a good idea of what information will be discussed. Once you know where the reading is headed, you can begin to read only the first sentence of each paragraph. Also the so called topic sentences, they give you the main idea of the paragraph. If you do not get the main idea in the topic sentence or if the paragraph greatly interests you, then you may want to skim more.

At the end of each topic sentence, your eyes should drop down through the rest of the paragraph to look for important pieces of information, such as names, dates, or events. Since the last few paragraphs may contain a conclusion or summary, you should stop skimming there and read them in detail. Keep in your

mind that your overall comprehension will be lower than reading in detail. While skimming you realize your grasping the main idea than skimming the topic correctly.

4. The advantages of Scanning and Skimming.

a. The advantage of Skimming

There are some advantages of skimming and scanning according to Grellet (1981:19) and Winarti (2010:15), they are as follows:

a. Skimming can aid students to go through the reading material quickly in order to get gist of the text.

b. Skimming help students to know how the text is organized.

c. Skimming can assist students to get an idea of the tone or the intonation of the writer. It means that, by reading using skimming the students can make reading material easier and they find out how the text is organized, simultaneously in this way they can improve an idea of the tone or the intonation of the writer.

b. The advantage of the scanning

There are some advantages of scanning, these are as follows :

a. Scanning helps the students only to try to locate specific information.

b. Scanning helps the students to follow the essential information from each line of the passage. c. Scanning helps students to use the time efficiently. Based on the statement above, for reading using scanning can help students to get information from the book and it aids to save time efficiently.

CONCLUSION

Reading is an important activity in life which one can update knowledge , it is not only a source of information and a pleasurable activity but also reading is a means of consolidating and extending one of the skills of the language. Therefore, the skill of reading is developed in societies with literacy taste and by enriching vocabulary.

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